

Validation of APOLLO3[®] self-shielding methods for stainless-steel reflectors calculations

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ABSTRACT

Stainless-steel reflectors are used in third-generation reactors such as EPR and in several SMR designs for their superior neutron reflection properties compared to light water, improving fuel efficiency and reducing reactor vessel fluence (so extending reactor lifetime); they are also cost-effective regarding their mechanical and corrosion resistance. However, steel main isotopes (e.g., ⁵⁶Fe, ⁵²Cr, ⁵⁸Ni) exhibit significant "dips" in scattering cross sections at specific energies (>10 keV), making the reflector nearly transparent at these points. Energy group structures in common lattice calculations lack the resolution to accurately model these scattering resonances, leading to over/underestimation of neutron interactions and leakage. A self-shielding model is required but the different models are primarily designed for the treatment of fuel heavy isotopes, not large metallic volumes like reflectors. In this article, we evaluate the accuracy of three different self-shielding methods available in the APOLLO3[®] code, candidates for modeling stainless-steel reflectors. It appears that the SubGroup method based on the REL383 energy mesh is the most accurate, closely matching Monte Carlo TRIPOLI-4[®] results on reactivity and fission rate distributions in the core. Further refinement in energy mesh or self-shielding of scattering cross sections could address remaining biases in the reflector.

Keywords: Steel reflector, self-shielding, validation, APOLLO3[®], TRIPOLI-4[®]

1. INTRODUCTION

Third-generation power reactors such as the EPR [1], as well as many current light-water SMR designs, including NuScale SMR [2], use stainless-steel reflectors.

This choice is dictated by physical and economic reasons. A stainless-steel thickness of about twenty centimeters improves the reflection of fast and intermediate neutrons compared to light water, which saves fuel, reduces the fluence on the reactor vessel, thus increasing reactor lifetime, flattens the power distribution, thus improving fuel utilization, and offers excellent mechanical properties (strength, ductility, toughness) and good corrosion resistance at a reasonable cost.

Unlike water, steel contains intermediate mass isotopes with predominantly scattering resonances, elastic scattering above 10 keV complemented by inelastic scattering above 800 keV (⁵⁶Fe, ⁵²Cr and ⁵⁸Ni mainly, see ⁵⁶Fe on Figure 1 for example). An important characteristic of the scattering cross sections (XS) of these nuclei is that they exhibit significant "dips," energy regions where interference effects between the resonant scattering cross section and the potential cross section lead to very low values for the total scattering cross section. The nucleus becomes almost transparent to neutrons at these energies due to a similarly low capture cross section. For example, for the dip at 24.54 keV associated with the 27.79 keV resonance of ⁵⁶Fe, the total cross section is on the order of 4 mbarns.

Energy group structures with a few hundred groups, commonly used in PWRs lattice calculations to obtain homogeneous two-group reflector cross sections, have a limited number of groups above 10 keV

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(e.g., about sixty for the APOLLO3® SHEM 281-group and REL 383-group libraries [3], for the SCALE AMPX 252-group library [4], and about 130 for the CASMO5 586-group library [5]).

Figure 1. ^{56}Fe – Capture (in blue), elastic (in red) and inelastic (in green) scattering cross section above 500 eV.

These energy structures do not allow for a detailed description of large scattering resonances. For example, group 50 of the SHEM281 mesh, which contains the 24.54 keV dip, covers the range [22.7 keV; 25.0 keV] in which the total cross section of ^{56}Fe varies between 4 mbarns and 4 barns (cf. Figure 4).

Figure 2. ^{56}Fe – total (in green) and elastic scattering XS (in red) around 24 keV + SHEM group number 50.

In the absence of a self-shielding (SSh) model, the lattice code will use the average cross section from the multigroup library, which will lead to an overestimation of interactions at the dip and, in the case of neutrons exiting the core, an underestimation of their propagation through the reflector and therefore of leakage. Self-shielding models have primarily been developed to deal with fuel isotopes and absorbers, making assumptions that may not be suited to large metallic volumes in which scattering reactions predominate.

The main objective of the present study is to ensure that the reflector effect of stainless-steel is correctly modeled by one or more of the different self-shielding methods available in the deterministic code APOLLO3®.

In the following chapter, we recall for these different self-shielding methods, detail the flux calculation options, and perform some preliminary studies on a “traverse” geometry representative of the core-reflector interface, describing the exact heterogeneous geometry of the fuel pins. Once certain options have been selected, a more detailed analysis is presented in chapter 3.

2. MAIN REFLECTOR CALCULATION OPTIONS

2.1. Traverse Geometry

The traverse motif chosen for the study is a simplified but representative geometry of the core-heavy reflector interface. It is a unidirectional 2D geometry, composed of a total of 42 square cells with a pitch of 1.26 cm: 12 fuel cells, followed by 18 homogeneous steel cells, then 12 water cells. Several spatial meshes, more or less refined, are used: one for self-shielding calculation and two for flux calculation. (cf. *Figure 3* and *Figure 4*). Reflective boundary conditions are applied on the four sides.

Figure 3. Traverse geometry, from top to bottom: self-shielding mesh, MAV and RAF meshes for flux calculation.

Figure 4. Zoom on MAV (on the left) and RAF (on the right) spatial meshes

2.2. APOLLO3® Self-Shielding Methods

Three self-shielding methods are a priori appropriate in APOLLO3® for the steel reflector treatment:

- the subgroup method of ECCO, called SGofEcco, used for Fast Reactors applications, which couples self-shielding and flux calculation via the source term (fission + slowing-down) that is assumed to be uncorrelated with the reaction term [6],
- a variant of the subgroup method, called SubGroup (or SGA3), introducing additional approximations (fine structure factorization leading to a slowing-down equation, decorrelation from flux calculation) [7],
- the Tone's method, originally dedicated to Fast Reactors calculations, relying on stronger approximations [8]: the source is assumed constant in each group g ($Q_i(E) \approx \bar{Q}_i^g$) but, above all, its fundamental assumption is that the flux $\phi_{ij}(E)$ in region j due to neutrons emitted in region i is proportional to the multigroup flux ϕ_{ij}^g with a coefficient $\alpha_j(E)$ depending only on the arrival region j . In [9], it has been shown that this method is applicable to Light Water Reactors (LWR) fuel for high energies ($> \text{keV}$).

The legacy Sanchez-Coste method currently used in APOLLO2 [10] for LWR production calculations, called "FineStructure" (FS) in its APOLLO3® implementation, is based on a heterogeneous-homogeneous equivalence and on some assumptions shared with the SubGroup method (pure elastic scattering problem, fine structure factorization). It is well suited to LWR assembly self-shielding in nominal situation but in the case of large metallic volumes, such as heavy reflectors, we demonstrated a long time ago [11] that this method was not relevant and it will only be used here for fuel self-shielding.

Different self-shielding methods can be used to treat the fuel and reflector independently; the seven combinations studied are presented in *Table I*. For fuel self-shielding, the FineStructure method can be used only with the 281-group energy structure SHEM281, whereas SGofEcco and SubGroup methods require the more refined 383-group structure REL383 to provide sufficiently accurate results [9].

Table I. : Fuel+reflector self-shielding methods combinations.

Combination	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
Energy structure	SHEM281			REL383			
Fuel SSh	FineStructure			SubGroup		SGofEcco	
Reflector SSh	Tone	SubGroup	SGofEcco	Tone	SubGroup	Tone	SGofEcco

2.3. Preliminary Analysis

Several preliminary studies were conducted to determine whether parameters other than the self-shielding method could significantly impact the results. These included:

- the number of self-shielding regions in the reflector, to verify the extent to which spectral degradation caused by scattering in the steel, as neutrons moves away from the core-reflector interface, impacts spatial self-shielding and, consequently, the reflector effect,
- the refinement of the spatial mesh for flux calculation (MAV or RAF),
- the spatial representation of the source, constant (SC) or linear (LS), in TDT-MOC solver.

2.3.1. Spatial self-shielding

With such a significant thickness of steel mainly supplied with neutrons from one side, a significant spatial self-shielding effect can be expected. However, since the cross sections values of metallic isotopes are small compared to that of ^{238}U , we chose to define self-shielding regions at least the size of a cell. We therefore focused on the evolution of reactivity as a function of the differentiation of the self-shielding of the cells. Starting with a calculation using a single self-shielded region for the entire reflector, we first differentiate the first cell in contact with the "core", then the first two, the first three, and so on. *Figure 5* gives an example for 5 different self-shielded regions in the reflector.

Figure 5. Traverse with five different self-shielded regions (different colors) in the reflector.

Flux calculation have been performed with the RAF mesh and linear source MOC. *Figure 6* shows similar trends for the three methods, Tone, SubGroup, and SGofEcco, with a rapid saturation effect:

- self-shielding of the reflector is mandatory because in its absence (number of SSh regions=0), the result is 50 to 100 pcm above the converged result, consequence of an overestimation of scattering reactions; the best apparent result without self-shielding is due to error compensation with the MOC-LS flux calculation, which overestimates the absorption of fuel by at least 100 pcm, as explained in detail in reference [12].
- convergence is almost achieved with a single SSh region for the entire steel.

Figure 6. Evolution of the APOLLO3[®]-TRIPOLI-4[®] difference as a function of the number of self-shielding regions for different couples fuel SSh/reflector SSh

2.3.2. Spatial mesh and source representation in TDT-MOC flux calculation

On this type of finite pattern, the macroscopic flux gradients are important; we ensure here the convergence of the spatial mesh (MAV or RAF) with regard to the spatial representation of the source (constant SC or linear LS) in the TDT-MOC calculations.

To this end, the four self-shielding combinations from the previous section were used again, assuming all 18 steel cells are distinguished, and the four combinations (MAV-SC, MAV-LS, RAF-SC, RAF-LS) were calculated (except for the SGofEcco/SGofEcco case with MAV-SC, which did not converge). The results are shown in Figure 7 as a histogram.

Figure 7. APOLLO3[®]-TRIPOLI-4[®] differences as a function of the spatial mesh and source representation in TDT-MOC

The following observations can be made:

- the RAF mesh appears sufficiently fine for constant MOC calculations since the results remain virtually unchanged when using linear MOC,
- the results with the RAF mesh are closest to TRIPOLI-4[®],
- the worst results are logically observed with the MAV mesh and constant MOC (additional bias of 100 pcm), and are only partially compensated by the use of the linear MOC,
- with given spatial mesh and source representation, the best agreement is obtained with the SubGroup method with an underestimation of 50 pcm using RAF mesh while the difference is on the order of -140 with SGofEcco and -200 pcm with Tone.

3. STUDY OF THE DIFFERENT FUEL/REFLECTOR SELF-SHIELDING COUPLES

This chapter focuses on the 7 combinations described in Table 1. Following, the preliminary results, all the calculations were performed distinguishing the self-shielding of the 18 reflector cells and using the RAF mesh and the constant MOC solver, which ensures the best convergence of APOLLO3 calculations regardless of the self-shielding methods.

The analysis concerns the reflector effect, with the study of the impact of the different SSh methods on the following parameters related to the core:

- Reactivity,
- Spatial distribution of the fission rate of ²³⁵U in the core (representative of the power distribution) and of two other "spectral indicators":
 - o ²³⁸U, whose fission cross section has a threshold around 1 MeV, thus with a fission rate representative of the fast flux, offering significant sensitivity to inelastic scattering,
 - o ²³⁷Np, whose fission cross section has a lower threshold, around 400 keV; its fission rate is therefore more sensitive to elastic slowing-down.
- Outgoing and incoming currents at the core-reflector interface, used to get 2-group discontinuity factors or reference multigroup albedo in industrial-type schemes.

3.1. Reactivity

The APOLLO3[®]- TRIPOLI-4[®] differences are shown in Figure 8.

Figure 8. APOLLO3®-TRIPOLI-4® reactivity biases for different fuel/reflector self-shielding combinations

The results show very low sensitivity to the self-shielding method used for the reflector (deviations less than 10 pcm between methods), with the main difference being the method used for the fuel. As already mentioned in the previous chapter, the SubGroup method yields the smallest deviations compared to TRIPOLI-4® (-50 pcm). It is interesting to note the very good performance of the fast Tone method, theoretically the least precise, whether combined with the FineStructure method with 281 groups or with the subgroup methods with 383 groups.

The following sections allow for a more refined comparison by examining the distribution of fission rates and flux in the core, as well as the current at the core-reflector interface.

3.2. Fission Rate Traverses

This section compares the 1-group fission rate traverses in the core for the three nuclei: ^{235}U , ^{238}U , and ^{237}Np . Figures 15, 16, and 17 below illustrate the evolution of the APOLLO3® errors against TRIPOLI-4® along the fuel cells. The constant values between $i-1$ and i (x-axis) corresponds to the values for cell number i . The y-axis on the right is the scale associated with the dashed curve representing the TRIPOLI-4® reference values. The y-axis on the left is associated with the deviation curves.

First, the distribution of uranium-235 fission rates in the fuel (Figure 9), which is representative of the power distribution, is very well calculated for all self-shielding methods, with a very slight overestimation that does not exceed 0.2% in the worst-case scenario in the cell closest to the reflector. The center-periphery shift does not exceed this 0.2% value.

Figure 9. APOLLO3® biases on ^{235}U fission rates along the fuel cells (extreme differences in legend).

The fission rates of ^{237}Np and ^{238}U (Figure 10), on the other hand, are slightly underestimated (due to normalization to production rates, in a manner almost equivalent to normalization to fission rates), with slightly higher maximum discrepancies: between 0.5 and 0.7%, given that the fission rate of ^{238}U is ten times lower than that of ^{235}U . When the SubGroup method is used in fuel, we observe slightly higher biases, on the order of 0.1 to 0.2% compared to FineStructure and SGofEcco, but the results remain satisfactory.

Figure 10. APOLLO3[®] biases on ^{237}Np (left) and ^{238}U (right) fission rates along the fuel cells.

3.3. Outgoing and incoming currents at the core-reflector interface

At the interface between the fuel and steel cells, an overall overestimation of the outgoing current and the incoming current (differences against TRIPOLI-4[®] for this latter are presented Figure 11 on the left) is observed, averaging around 3%, with locally larger biases in certain groups, reaching approximately 10% for the outgoing current and up to 30% for the incoming current. The significant fluctuations that appear with energy, suggest a biased distribution of elastic scattering between $g \rightarrow g$ and $g \rightarrow g+1$ (above a few hundred eV, the average lethargy widths of the SHEM281 and REL383 groups are around 0.15 and 0.08 respectively, while the maximum lethargy gain on ^{56}Fe is around 0.07; the possibility of a $g \rightarrow g+2$ scattering is therefore quite limited). The different combinations of self-shielding methods yield very similar results, none of them truly stands out from the others. Solving this problem involves either self-shielding of the scattering XS, a method currently unavailable in APOLLO3[®], or the use of a finer energy mesh such as the RNR1760 structure with 1760 groups. In this case, the fluctuations are effectively completely attenuated (Figure 11 on the right).

Figure 11. APOLLO3[®] biases on incoming current at the core reflector-interface, on the left for the different SSH combinations with the 281 or 383-group energy meshes, on the right for the SubGroup+Tone combination with the 383 group (green curve) and the 1760-group (blue curve) structures

4. CONCLUSIONS

The study of the different methods in the APOLLO3[®] code (SubGroup, SGofEcco, and Tone) for handling the self-shielding of a steel reflector in light water reactors, revealed the following points:

- the spatial self-shielding of the steel reflector is weak: a single self-shielding region is necessary and sufficient to properly cover its entire thickness.
- for the traverse geometry studied, it was necessary to adopt a refined mesh (RAF) rather than a simple windmill mesh (MAV). Using a linear spatial source for the flux in TDT-MOC does not significantly improve results compared to the more commonly used constant approximation.
- given a specific fuel self-shielding method, the “core” results are virtually independent of the self-shielding method used for the reflector. The limited biases observed in the reactivity compared to TRIPOLI-4[®] cannot therefore be easily attributed to it, especially since the power distribution is very well reproduced (center-to-periphery shift is not exceeding 0.2%).

Additional results, not presented here, show that energetic fluctuations of the currents, here observed at the core-reflector interface, persist in the reflector with a trend to an overall overestimation after a few centimeters of penetration. In the absence of self-shielding of group-to-group scattering, only a finer energy mesh (with 1760 groups) allows a significant reduction of these effects.

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